

The influence of school principals' management on school efficiency: Evidence from Italian schools

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Summary

1. This study investigates how school principals' managerial practices influence school performance in Italian middle schools.
2. Using a multidimensional approach, school efficiency is assessed through both student test scores and indicators of school climate, based on national data from INVALSI.
3. The analysis reveals that managerial practices—especially monitoring, target setting, and people management—significantly contribute to higher school efficiency.
4. Moreover, it is not only the individual practices but also their combination that drives better outcomes.
5. These findings underscore the importance of strengthening school leadership through targeted support, training, and policy development.

1. Introduction

School principals play a central role in shaping the quality and effectiveness of education. Their managerial practices influence not only academic outcomes but also the broader school environment (Di Liberto, Schivardi, & Sulis, 2015). Recent reforms in many education systems have expanded the autonomy of school leaders, based on the belief that increased managerial discretion can enhance school efficiency. However, the evidence on how principals' practices affect performance remains mixed (Creagh et al., 2025; Ruloff, & Petko, 2025). In particular, there is limited understanding of how different managerial activities contribute to school efficiency, especially when performance is defined beyond test scores to include aspects like school climate.

This policy brief summarises new evidence on how principals' managerial practices affect school performance in Italy (Mergoni et al., 2025). Drawing on data from a nationally representative sample of 8th-grade students, the study models school performance through a multidimensional lens, combining test scores with perceptions from students, parents, and teachers. The research introduces a novel methodological approach that captures both individual and combined effects of managerial practices. By focusing on areas such as monitoring, target setting, personnel management, and operational organisation, we identify which practices are most strongly linked to higher school efficiency. The findings have important implications for how educational leadership is supported and developed across schools.

2. Data and Methodology

This study uses data from the 2018/2019 school year collected by INVALSI, the Italian

National Evaluation Committee for Education. The dataset includes information on student test scores in mathematics, Italian, and English, alongside survey responses from school principals on their managerial practices and perceptions of the school climate. The final sample consists of 544 middle schools from a nationally representative subsample, after excluding units with missing data.

School performance is evaluated using a Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) approach, a method that assesses how efficiently schools transform inputs into outputs (Mergoni, Emrouznejad, & De Witte, 2025). Outputs include both cognitive outcomes - measured by student test scores - and softer outcomes related to school climate, such as attitudes and satisfaction levels among students, parents, and teachers. Inputs are captured by students' socioeconomic status.

To examine the influence of principals' practices, the study applies both unconditional and conditional versions of the DEA model. The conditional approach adjusts for the managerial practices of school leaders, allowing for an analysis of how these contextual variables shape efficiency. Managerial practices are grouped into five areas: monitoring, target setting, people management, operations, and leadership, following the example by Agasisti, Falzetti, & Soncin (2020). This framework enables a comprehensive and nuanced assessment of the link between school management and performance.

3. Results

The analysis reveals several key findings regarding the influence of school principals' managerial practices on school efficiency.

First, principals' practices are significantly associated with school performance, particularly when the performance is assessed through both academic results and school climate indicators. This result is in line with previous such as Agasisti, Bowers, & Soncin (2019), who observed differences in the educational outcomes depending on the different leadership styles. While the unconditional efficiency scores reveal variations in schools' ability to transform inputs into outputs, the conditional model shows that these differences are closely linked to the quality and type of managerial practices implemented.

The study introduces a quantitative measure to assess the overall influence of principal's managerial practices and their interactions on school performance. Among the five managerial dimensions - monitoring, target setting, people management, operations, and leadership - monitoring stands out as the most influential. Schools where principals actively monitor performance, regularly assess progress, and use data to inform decisions tend to be more efficient. Target setting and people management also show strong positive associations with efficiency. In particular, clear educational goals and supportive actions aimed at teachers' development contribute substantially to improved outcomes.

In contrast, leadership and operations practices, while still relevant, exhibit a smaller marginal impact. This suggests that while it is important to define roles and manage day-to-day operations, these areas alone are less decisive for driving performance unless combined with effective monitoring and people-focused strategies.

An important innovation of this study lies in its ability to evaluate the joint effect of managerial practices. The interaction between

different practices shows that combining different practices in general leads to better results. Combining monitoring with target setting or people management leads to the strongest impacts on efficiency. This means that it is not only individual practices that matter, but also how they complement one another.

Interestingly, we find that not all schools benefit equally from similar practices. This variation suggests that the effectiveness of managerial strategies may depend on contextual factors such as school size, regional differences, or existing institutional support. However, even when these differences are accounted for, the association between good management and school efficiency remains robust.

Finally, the results highlight that managerial practices are not just administrative tools, but core drivers of educational performance. They influence not only student achievement but also the quality of the learning environment as perceived by students, teachers, and parents. This reinforces the idea that school leadership should be evaluated and supported not just in terms of authority, but also in terms of managerial effectiveness.

4. Policy Recommendations

The findings of this study offer valuable insights for improving school performance through more effective managerial practices. Recommendations can be addressed at three levels:

- school providers,
- national governments, and
- supra-national organisations such as the European Commission.

School providers should prioritize the recruitment, training, and continuous support of principals with strong managerial

capacities. Emphasis should be placed on enhancing practices in monitoring, target setting, and people management, as these have the greatest impact on school efficiency. Monitoring involves the systematic collection and use of data to inform decisions, a practice that should be embedded in everyday school operations. Providers should equip principals with tools to regularly assess school progress and ensure that data use becomes an integral part of school culture.

Additionally, school providers should facilitate the exchange of good practices among principals. Peer learning platforms or regional leadership clusters can help principals reflect on their management approaches and learn from high-performing schools. Finally, they should provide targeted support to principals in low-performing schools, focusing on the adoption and implementation of proven managerial strategies.

National education ministries should design policies that systematically develop and support managerial skills among school leaders. Leadership preparation programmes must go beyond instructional leadership and focus on actionable managerial competencies—especially in monitoring, setting goals, and managing staff. Such programmes should be integrated into both pre-service training and ongoing professional development.

Governments should also create national frameworks for evaluating and recognising good managerial practices. Rather than relying solely on student test scores, performance evaluations should include assessments of how principals manage their schools, interact with staff, and implement strategies to improve the school climate.

Moreover, governments should ensure that school leaders are granted sufficient

autonomy to apply managerial practices effectively. However, this autonomy must be accompanied by clear accountability systems and support structures to avoid exacerbating inequalities among schools.

The European Commission can play a key role in promoting evidence-based leadership practices across Member States by supporting cross-country research and knowledge exchange. Initiatives such as Erasmus+ should be expanded to include leadership and management training for school principals. European funding could be directed towards transnational projects that identify and test best practices in school management.

Additionally, the Commission should encourage the development of a European framework for effective school leadership. Such a framework could guide national policy reforms and ensure a coherent approach to building managerial capacity across diverse education systems.

Finally, the Commission can support benchmarking efforts by developing indicators that capture not only academic outcomes but also the quality of school management and climate. These indicators can inform policy at all levels and ensure that managerial practices are recognised as central to school improvement.

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